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Analysis of pesticide residues in olive oil and other vegetable oils

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ABSTRACT

Pesticide residue analysis in olive oil presents difficulties due to the high amount of co-eluted compounds resulting in high matrix effect. Different extraction/clean-up methods including gel permeation chromatography, liquid/liquid extraction, solid-phase extraction and other extraction methods are applied to overcome these difficulties. Recent approaches such as the addition of the freezing-out step and the application of Enhanced Matrix Removal-Lipid sorbent (EMR-Lipid) are reported. Gas chromatography and liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry are considered the gold standard technologies covering a wide scope of pesticides. This review recapitulates the methods most widely used for the determination of pesticide residues in vegetable oils. As a continuation of previous reviews, the work conducted is an update review of methods from 2006 in this field, evaluating their strengths and limitations. Main analytical parameters of the different extraction procedures and detection methods are discussed in terms of recoveries, robustness, limit of quantification, and matrix effect.

Keywords: Olive oil; Extraction methods; Analytical methods; Recoveries; LOQ; Matrix effect

1. Introduction

Olive trees are prone to various diseases caused by pests, fungi and weeds. Among those diseases that affect olive trees, there are those caused by fungi (eye of peacock, black mold, and verticilliose) and those caused by insects (olive fly, olive moth, psyllids, thrips, cochineal, neiroun, and leopard moth). The olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*, Rossi) is the main disease attacking olive trees in Mediterranean countries causing reduction of olive production due to precocious downfall [1]. The control of parasites and diseases through pesticides application helps to maintain high levels of olive oil production and other vegetable oils. However, the use of pesticides is also associated with certain risks resulting in potential contamination [2]. The residual fraction of pesticides remaining in the fruit may persist and be retrieved in the final oil especially for high lipophilic pesticides. As a consequence, consumers are indirectly exposed to pesticides, hence the increasing concern of food quality and safety worldwide.

The concern of food safety brought up the attention for scientific research efforts to develop the optimum extraction and analytical methods for pesticide residues analysis in vegetable oil. This task is challenging due to the complexity of oil matrices. During a period of twelve-year, from 2006 to 2017, a number of studies dealing with the monitoring of pesticide residues in complex vegetable oil matrices have been published. Highly selective, sensitive and accurate procedures were implemented. They involve two main stages: the pesticide extraction procedure and the analytical determination method.

A quick throwback on the extraction procedures adopted for the determination of pesticide residues in olive oil from 2001 to 2005 reveals a reliance on liquid/liquid extraction followed by solid phase extraction (SPE) using alumina column or C₁₈ cartridges [3-8]. From 2006 to 2016, SPE was still adopted [9]. Very recently SPE procedures were developed with the use of magnetic nanoparticles and molecularly imprinted polymers [10,11]. Several authors have reported studies using matrix-solid-phase-dispersion (MSPD) [12-16] and solid-phase matrix microextraction (SPME) [17]. However, dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE) is the procedure most commonly applied so far [18-31] especially with the availability of new sorbents. Despite its high organic solvent consumption, gel permeation chromatography (GPC) [32-36] was still adopted as well but the last papers published were on 2006 and 2007. Other promising studies dealing with new extraction procedures based on liquid/liquid extraction (L/L) [12,37-40] rose,

such as liquid/liquid microextraction [41] and dissociation extraction (DE) that were recently developed [42,43].

Analytical methods employing different analyzers have been reported. The earliest studies reported analysis by gas chromatography coupled to flame ionization detector (GC-FID) [17,41], gas chromatography coupled to electron capture detector (GC-ECD) [32,35,43] and to nitrogen phosphorus detector (GC-NPD) [9,12]. In spite of the low selectivity of diode array detectors (DAD), in recent years, some studies reported analysis on liquid chromatography (LC) coupled to DAD for the determination of pesticide residues in vegetable oils [10,11,25,40]. However, mass spectrometry coupled to gas chromatography (GC-MS and GC-MS/MS) [19-24,33-35,44] is the most used technology regarding the targeted non-polar compounds, due to its high selectivity. Polar compounds are assumed to be partially removed during the industrial extraction process of olive oil, but the probability of the presence of polar and medium-polar pesticide residues made liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry also indispensable in the analysis of pesticide residues in vegetable oils (LC-MS and LC-MS/MS) [18,20-24,29,45,46]. Some studies reported pesticide residues analysis in vegetable oils by LC coupled to a time-of-flight mass spectrometry detector (LC-ToF-MS), investigating the improvement of high selective detectors in avoiding matrix interferences [13,14,23,37].

In this review, following a brief summary of the international regulation, reported procedures for pesticide residues analysis in olive oil and other vegetable oils are discussed with all their advantages and limitations. Evaluation of their efficiency is made based on the scope of pesticides covered, the recovery rates obtained, the relative standard deviations (RSDs) achieved, the limit of quantification (LOQs) reached, and the reduced matrix effect.

2. Regulations

Due to the extensive use of pesticides and the increasing food safety control, the determination of pesticide residues in vegetable oil became a priority. Analytical methods should be validated as mentioned in the framework of European pesticide regulation EC No 1107/2009 [47]. Maximum residue limits (MRLs) were not only fixed to olives, sunflower seeds and soybeans but also to their processed oil by considering the processing factors.

The Codex Alimentarius, established by the FAO and the World Health

Organization in 1963, develops harmonized international food standards. For virgin olive oil, MRLs were set for carbaryl (25 mg kg⁻¹), cypermethrin (0.5 mg kg⁻¹), fenthion (1 mg kg⁻¹), kresoxim-methyl (0.7 mg kg⁻¹), and trifloxystrobin (0.9 mg kg⁻¹). For refined olive oil, MRLs were established only for cypermethrin (0.5 mg kg⁻¹) and trifloxystrobin (1.2 mg kg⁻¹) [48].

The Japan Food Chemical Research Foundation has established a positive list system for agricultural chemical residues in Foods that includes MRLs for only three pesticides in edible virgin olive oil: carbaryl (25 mg kg⁻¹), fenthion (1 mg kg⁻¹) and methidathion (2 mg kg⁻¹) [49].

The MRLs set by the European Union (EU) are more stringent. MRLs are established by the regulation EC No 396/2005 [50]. They cover a much broader spectrum of pesticides; 365 pesticides for oil seeds, 396 pesticides for oil fruits and 472 pesticides for olives for oil production. MRLs are in a range of 0.01-0.05 mg kg⁻¹ [51].

Following the EU regulation No 1274/2011, accounting for the usual oil production standard yield of 20% of the olive harvest, a default factor of 5 may be applied to fat soluble substances [52]. This default processing factor (PF) for olive oil is clearly not optimum in three cases: (i) in the case of non-fat soluble pesticides, (ii) where the MRL is set at the LOQ, (iii) and where there is no evidence of the pesticide being authorized for the use on olives for oil production. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) considers that for pesticides that are not fat soluble, a default processing factor of 1 should be applied unless specific processing studies are available demonstrating that a different value is appropriate (e.g. dimethoate, PF: 0.3) [53]. Further guidance is needed to ensure a consistent approach for the enforcement of MRLs for olive oil, particularly on the use of processing factors. The PF depends on the olive oil extraction procedure and may be variable.

If the same approach is to be applied for soybean oil and sunflower oil, the production yield percentage for soybean is about 18% [54] and the pesticide residues will accumulate in the oil by a factor of 5 as well. As for sunflower oil, the yield is 40.6% [54] and the default processing factor in this case is 2.5.

Table 1 shows the different MRLs set in the world for olive oil. Each market has its own set of MRLs. The difference between MRLs set for the same compound and the same commodity by different world regulations could be a bit confusing especially for the exporting and importing of olive oil through the world. The absence of MRLs for some compounds in certain regulations can be confusing when it comes to the trade market of olive oil and other vegetable oils. Similar problems

are encountered for pesticides authorized in some countries and banned in others. Successful trade starts with having the right information and MRLs requirements across the global market. As example, to be allowed to export products to the EU, the residue levels must be in compliance with the Regulation EC No 396/2005. Authorized pesticides for application on olive trees in Spain, the main EU country producing olive oil, are listed in [Table 2](#). They include herbicides, fungicides and insecticides/acaricides [\[55\]](#) with their corresponding MRLs according to EU regulations.

3. Sample extraction and clean-up procedures

One of the main challenging problems in the analysis of pesticide residues in olive oil and other vegetable oils is related to the high matrix effect. The matrix effect depends on the complexity of the matrix. The composition of olive oil varies depending on the botanical variety. As average, olive oils contain 100% fats; 13.8% saturated and 72.9% unsaturated fatty acids [\[55\]](#). The occurrence of matrix effect for olive oil cannot be avoided in multiresidue methods (MRM), although minimizing it is possible by the dilution of the oil sample with the solvent of analysis in order to reduce the presence of matrix interference [\[41\]](#). Sample treatment of oils before the chromatographic analysis should allow the removal of high molecular fat components avoiding the damages that could affect the analysis and the maintenance of analytical instruments. The removal of fat can be accompanied with the removal of non-polar pesticides resulting in low recoveries. Different approaches have been proposed as GPC, L/L extraction, SPE, d-SPE, MSPD, and SPME. These approaches are summarized in [Table 3](#). Each technique provides strengths and limitations in pesticide determination.

3.1. GPC

GPC was considered years ago the most common and robust methodology used for the analysis of pesticide residues in high fat matrices due to its stability. GPC sample preparation is a useful tool for separating high molecular weight of fat components of oils (triglycerides) from the low molecular weight of pesticides. It is appropriate for both polar and non-polar analytes. Therefore it can be effectively used to clean-up extracts containing a broad range of compounds; Frenich et al., reported a survey of 100 pesticides in olive oil by GPC [\[33\]](#). It is indeed an efficient method

because it decreases the damage to the analytical instrumentation, liners, and columns. This extraction method is amenable to automation. It yields reproducible results because it reduces operator errors. GPC was mostly adopted till 2007 [32,44,56]. It has disadvantages since it uses high amounts of organic hazardous solvents (e.g., cyclohexane/ dichloromethane), which results in high chemical consumption generating a lot of waste that requires safe disposal. Additionally, a disadvantage of GPC is its time consumption that can be considered as a bottleneck in the laboratories systems. The processing time of each sample is approximately 1 h; about 14-23 min for the elution of the fat components [56], 26 min for the elution of pesticides, and about 5 min for the rinsing of the column. Sometimes, the extract needs an additional clean-up step before chromatographic analysis because the collected fraction may be accompanied with minor oil matrix traces. The two fractions of triglycerides and low molecular weight pesticides may overlap, resulting in a loss of some non-polar pesticides such as acrinathrin (logP: 6.46), phenotrin (logP: 7.54) and bromopropylate (logP: 5.4).

Followed by GC-ECD analysis, studies showed that the procedure using GPC extraction yielded good recovery rates between 91 and 124% [35] and good RSDs rates below 10%. The limit of quantification obtained (below 20 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) was satisfactory considering the corresponding pesticides studied because their maximum residue level could be easily verified. Followed by GC-MS/MS analysis, good recovery rates were also obtained between 70-110% and 89-105% [33-35] with low RSDs, satisfying the European Union Guideline. Certainly, lower limit of quantification are reached by GC-MS/MS analysis (below 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) [35].

3.2. Liquid/liquid partitioning

L/L extraction is an extensive separation technique. It is generally followed by a clean-up step (GPC or SPE) but it also can be applied as the only extraction step. The traditional approach for the extraction of pesticides from oil is the use of a water/miscible solvent such as methanol or acetonitrile, followed by L/L partitioning with n-hexane. The disadvantage of this technique resides in its consumption of large quantity of solvents and in its difficulty to be automated. The optimization of L/L extraction procedure using the appropriate organic solvent has been studied by T.D. Nguyen et al. (2010) [28]. Partition effects using different solvents (petroleum ether saturated with acetonitrile and n-hexane) have been reported. The most satisfactory RSD results were obtained using n-hexane as extraction solvent (1.9-7.2%)

[28].

A recent procedure was developed based on a dissociated extraction. It consists of an extraction with perchloric acid in acetonitrile, followed by clean-up of acetonitrile by hexane. Dissociation extraction using acidified acetonitrile instead of pure acetonitrile allows the use of a lower solvent volume [42]. It is a quick and simple approach that also allows obtaining purer sample extracts by the removal of acids and hydrophilic substances from extract [42,43]. Based on Zayat et al., the determination of 40 pesticides by dissociation extraction with acetonitrile, hexane and dichloromethane followed by GC-MS analysis showed good recovery rates (85-115%), good repeatability (RSD < 10%) and LOQ values between 3 and 150 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ [42]. The results obtained, based on GC-ECD and targeting azoles pesticides likewise indicated good recovery rates between 85% and 115% with RSD values below 10%. The obtained limits of quantitation ranged from 3 to 300 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. LOQs reached are below the MRLs set by the EU for the majority of pesticides studied [43]. However, this developed technique is not suitable for the analysis of hydrophobic pesticides which are not protonated in acidified acetonitrile. This is the case of a wide range of pesticides including pyrethroids, organochlorines, dinitroanilines and carbamates.

The determination of triazoles residues in edible oils was recently developed using an air-assisted L/L microextraction [41]. This procedure consists of an extraction with dimethyl sulfoxide of oil samples diluted with hexane. Therefore the mixture is rapidly aspirated and dispersed with a syringe. It is a simple and rapid extraction that requires a short analysis time. It showed satisfactory results in terms of recoveries with a range of 71 and 96% by GC-FID.

3.3. MSPD

The application of MSPD consists of a direct blending of the sample with a solid support such as aminopropyl (NH_2), octadecylsilyl (C_{18}), octyl (C_8), Florisil, and silica. MSPD using silica gel as sorbent material has been reported for the analysis of 14 organochlorine pesticides in edible vegetable oils and have resulted in recoveries between 69.6 and 105.3% and RSD results below 15%. LOD reached were between 0.04 and 0.74 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ [16]. MSPD using aminopropyl as sorbent material with a clean-up performed with Florisil was reported in 2005 by Ferrer et al., for the analysis of pesticide residues in olives and olive oil. This study covered 13 pesticides (dimethoate, simazine, atrazine, diuron, terbuthylazine, methylparathion, pirimiphos methyl, endosulfan I, endosulfan II, endosulfan sulfate,

cypermethrin and deltamethrin). It was proven to be effective [57]. Cleaner extracts are obtained in MSPD when a preliminary liquid/liquid extraction of olive oil is applied [57]. Subsequently, MSPD using aminopropyl as dispersant was envisaged in two other studies for the analysis of pesticide residues in olive oil [12,14]. The MSPD procedures followed by LC-ToF-MS showed good recovery results (81-111%) and low LODs ($1-5 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) for specific compounds (simazine, atrazine, diuron and terbuthylazine) [14].

The evaluation of two different adsorbents (alumina and Florisil) and two different sorbents (C_{18} and PSA) in MSPD was highlighted. When the alumina was packed in the base of reversed-phase materials (C_{18}), high matrix interference was observed for most of the pesticides studied (dimethoate, malathion, carbaryl, simazine, terbuthylazine, atrazine, and diuron). The recovery rate obtained was very low and unsatisfactory, in a range of 17.3-38.5%, except for atrazine (112.4%). The extract obtained from MSPD column including a mixture of PSA/oil blend and alumina resulted in a high recovery and a high matrix effect due to the interference from the sorbent itself. The extraction column prepared with Florisil/PSA resulted in a cleaner extract but low recoveries were obtained. The best results and the cleanest extracts were obtained with the use of PSA and Florisil/GCB (70:30). Recoveries obtained were between 72.6% and 91.3% with RSD in a range of 5.3-14.2%. LOQs reached were within $2.5-9 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ [13].

MSPD is a non-automated procedure and does not fit routine analysis requirement because it is a manual process, thus time consuming. Solvent volume is an important extraction parameter to be considered in MSPD. There are no studies where a large number of pesticides were examined in olive oil using the MSPD techniques. A survey comparing the efficacy of the determination of fenthion and its metabolites in oil samples by MSPD and L/L extraction was conducted. MSPD was at least twice as sensitive and required ten times less sample weight in the experimental conditions tested [12]. Lower LOQs were obtained ($30 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) than with L/L extraction ($100 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). MSPD has other advantages such as the use of smaller amount of solvent and reducing matrix interferences. With MSPD followed by LC-MS/MS determination, a signal suppression of only 20% was observed [58].

3.4. SPE

SPE technique was considered as alternative for GPC. It consumes less solvent

and generates little waste. Different SPE cartridges were subject to study in the scope of the determination of pesticide residues in olive oil (alumina, C₁₈, Florisil, Envicarb). Good recovery results were achieved by using Envicarb SPE between 70 and 106% [9]. Moreover, highly polar compounds can be recovered: acephate (logP: -0.85), phenol (logP: 1.51), 1,4-dioxane (logP: -0.27), and oxamyl (logP: -1.2). SPE extraction method using Envicarb cartridges has advantages over both MSPD and L/L extraction as lower LOQs are reached for organophosphorus compounds (e.g. fenthion, LOQ: 4.6 µg kg⁻¹). This comparison was possible because the same analytical instrument (GC-NPD) was used in these two studies [9,12]. SPE Envicarb was successfully applied following a microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) in one of the studies, targeting 9 organophosphorus in olive oil [59]. Recovery rates achieved were above 70% except for fenthion, chlorpyrifos and diazinon. An interesting feature of MAE is that it reduces time and solvent consumption. This technique was proposed by Fuentes et al., and Hernández Borges et al., for fatty matrices as avocado, avocado oil and olive oil [59,60].

In addition to the traditional SPE cartridges, the use of carbon nanotube has been recently introduced. Different types of carbon nanotube cartridges are available; multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) and carboxylated single walled (SWCNTs). High extraction efficiency is obtained with the SWCNTs due to the small diameter of the nanotubes and the high surface area per volume [61]. Moreover, higher sorption capabilities were demonstrated with SWCNTs and better results were obtained for the studied pesticides (chlortoluron, diuron, atrazine, simazine, terbuthylazin-desethyl, dimethoate, malathion and parathion) [62]. The limits of detection reached were between 0.0015 and 0.003 µg mL⁻¹. The RSD obtained was below 9%. The remarkable advantage of these cartridges is that they can be reused at least 100 times without losing performance capability. In 2016, SPE using zirconium (Z-Sep) has been also applied for high fatty matrices commodities including olive oil [18,19], and was demonstrated to be effective, resulting in clean extracts. The SPE is typically time consuming. With other SPE clean-up approaches that include the use of multipurpose sampler (MPS) with an automated SPE option, better recoveries and reproducibility results can be achieved. Following the SPE clean-up steps, the MPS can introduce the sample extract directly to LC/MS or GC/MS.

Very recently, SPE using polystyrene coated magnetic nanoparticles [10] and dual molecularly imprinted polymers (DL-MISPE) [11] have been applied. The first method was developed for pyrethroids including tetramethrin, fenpropathrin, cypermethrin, decamethrin, fenvalerate, permethrin, acrinathrin, and bifenthrin.

This technique is different from other SPE techniques which use disposable adsorbents; the magnetic adsorbents can be collected, cleaned and recycled. It is efficient because it shows good recovery rates 83-113% with RSD below 12% and low LOQs in a range of 0.0891-0.1994 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ as reported in the study. This procedure showed low matrix interference. It is remarkable that despite its low selectivity, pesticide residues were determined using a LC-DAD. As for the dual layer of molecularly imprinted polymers SPE, it was applied for the extraction of triazines and organophosphorus compounds in olive oil. This work consists of using two MIP layers as specific sorbents [11]. It showed good recovery rates and it is less time consuming. This latter method has some advantages over d-SPE method. The comparison of extraction methods reported by different studies is possible when the determination is performed by the same analytical instrument for the same class of pesticides. Consequently, the comparison of the results obtained with DL-MISPE and d-SPE using zirconium is possible as studies were reported following the determination by the same analytical instrument (LC-DAD). Lower LOQs are obtained by DL-MISPE (6 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) [11] than with d-SPE using zirconium (180 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) for a triazine compound, terbuthylazine [15]. One of the disadvantages of the MIP is related to its lack of reproducibility; the data obtained with different batches of MIP are not reproducible [63].

Solid-phase microextraction SPME in headspace mode was also developed to overcome the complexity problems in sample preparation; it requires short time, does not need a clean-up step for sample and generates no waste. It is a fast adsorption/desorption technique where the coated fiber is suspended above the sample. There are different kinds of coatings (polydimethylsiloxane PDMS, PDMS-divinylbenzene, and Carbowax-PDMS fibers). Good recoveries were obtained with headspace-SPME between 80 and 106% [17]. The studies performed by SPME do not cover a large scope of pesticides.

3.5. *d-SPE*

Efforts have been invested in the d-SPE procedure for the analysis of pesticide residues in vegetable oil. A rapid and simple clean-up step was in need in this field to be implemented in routine analysis laboratories. Many studies were focused on QuEChERS extractions for pesticide residues analysis in vegetable oil [21-24]. This procedure is very simple and consumes less solvent compared to other established techniques [64]. It is also effective for numerous hydrophobic analytes. Selective

removal of lipid interferences, in order to minimize matrix effect, is possible with the combination of different sorbents and more interestingly with the availability of new sorbents. The use of adequate clean-up sorbents is also important for the instrument maintenance, as it reduces damages to the instrumentation (liner, column).

Compared to MSPD, d-SPE clearly was demonstrated to have advantages regarding recoveries. A comparative study of MSPD extraction procedure using aminopropyl as sorbent material and a Florisil cartridge and d-SPE procedure using GCB, C₁₈ and PSA as clean-up sorbents was reported. Recoveries between 70 and 130% were achieved for 72% of the analytes extracted by d-SPE and for only 57% of analytes processed by MSPD [29]. However in terms of matrix effect, minor effects are observed using MSPD procedure whereas in term of LOQs, satisfactory concentrations are reached with both extraction procedures (10 µg kg⁻¹).

Care should be taken when selecting d-SPE sorbents. Nowadays, the d-SPE approach is based on PSA, C₁₈, and GCB. PSA is used to remove fatty acids, GCB is used to remove pigments and sterols and C₁₈ is used to remove non-polar interferences. Regarding LODs and LOQs, the PSA-GCB-C₁₈ combination provided the best results from this aspect (LOQs < 1 µg kg⁻¹). When QuEChERS is applied, the highest matrix effect (with an average of -40%) obtained by LC-MS/MS for the analysis of olive oil is when PSA and MgSO₄ were used as clean-up sorbents. Lowest matrix effect was observed with the use of PSA, MgSO₄ and C₁₈. The lowest matrix effect of all with an average of 25% was observed with the combination of the four sorbents (PSA, MgSO₄, C₁₈ and GCB) and not only for olive oil but also for rapeseed oil, sunflower oil and palm oil [22]. However, despite the cleanest extract obtained with this latter combination of sorbents, the lowest recoveries (53-131%) and the highest RSD (8-41%) were observed too [22]. Studies showed that the PSA-C₁₈-MgSO₄ combination gave the best results with the highest recoveries and the lowest RSDs (3-19%) except for the two organophosphates, mevinphos and acephate [22]. In terms of recoveries and as reported in other studies, the combination of Florisil and MgSO₄ anhydrous gave very good recovery rates (82-107%). The combination of PSA and Florisil as clean-up sorbents also yielded good recovery rates (75-112%) [28]. Among all sorbents used (Florisil, GCB, C₁₈, PSA and Florisil combination), the cleaner extract and the best RSD results (2-15%) were obtained with Florisil [28]. The concern using PSA is related to the fact that it can cause the hydrolyzation of base-sensitive pesticides. This susceptible problem can be solved by adding formic acid to the final extract to adjust the pH [65]. There was a concern about using GCB;

the clean-up step using GCB resulted in good recoveries but it depends on the target list of pesticides. In some studies, GCB was demonstrated to be adsorbing not only the matrix component but also pesticides that have planar ring structure. This is because of its great specific surface. It is the case of hexachlorobenzene, chlorothalonil, boscalid, prochloraz, carbendazim and thiabendazole [9]. Amitraz, bromacil, dichlorofluanid, dichlorobenil, fenithrothion and pendimethalin also showed low recoveries with GCB due to their planar structure that has high affinity toward GCB [28]. The replacement of GCB by activated charcoal (AC) was described in some studies in order to obtain better recoveries [31]. AC's surface area ($900 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) is higher than GCB's ($100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), which means better adsorption of hydrophobic impurities but the loss of non-polar pesticides could not be guaranteed. It is important to note that optimizing the amount of sorbents used is necessary to maintain the balance between recoveries and matrix effect or else unsatisfactory results could be obtained.

Other selective materials have been developed and authors have reported the use of multi walled carbon nanotube (MWCNs) as a clean-up sorbent in pesticide residues analysis in food [66] and particularly for peanut oil [27]. Different types of MWCNs differing by their internal diameter, length and specific area, have been evaluated. The cleaner extract was obtained with MWCNTs of an outside diameter between 10 and 20 nm, length from 10 to 30 μm and special surface area of $200 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ [27]. Nine organophosphorus were studied using this particular sorbent. Good recovery rates were obtained between 91 and 112% and the RSDs obtained were lower than 8.5%. LODs reached were between 0.7 and $1.6 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$.

Modified QuEChERS sample preparation using amine modified graphene ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH-G}$) as reversed-dispersive solid phase extraction material has been reported in 2013 by Guan et al. [30]. Good recovery rates were obtained between 70.5 and 100%. Low RSDs <13% were achieved. Low LODs were reached ($0.1\text{-}8.3 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). Amine modified graphene has been demonstrated to have better clean-up performance than G (graphene), PSA, MWCN and GCB.

Lately, in the scope of further modifications to QuEChERS, a new commercially available sorbent based on zirconium (Z-Sep) was developed for the analysis of pesticide residues in oil. The Z-Sep product consists of both C_{18} and zirconium bound to silica. The C_{18} binds fats through hydrophobic interaction, while the zirconium acts as a Lewis acid, attracting compounds with electron donating groups. Modified QuEChERS using Zirconium in the clean-up step has been applied with success. The reported LOQs for d-SPE using GC-MS/MS for most of the

compounds were between 0.09 and 2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Good recovery rates were obtained, 74-101%. Cleaner extracts are obtained with Z-Sep comparing to the conventional QuEChERS [6]. The introduction of zirconium in the clean-up step has generally reduced the matrix effect. It was demonstrated to be between [30%] for most carbamates studied by LC-MS/MS [20]. However, Z-Sep may have some drawbacks. Significant removal of co-extractives interference was achieved using Z-Sep but there is a probability that with zirconium, non-polar pesticides may also be removed in the clean-up procedure causing suppression of results and low recoveries [20,25]. The recovery of some non-polar compounds such as bromopropylate (logP: 5.4) are adversely affected. Additionally, an interaction may occur between zirconium and pesticides that contain phosphate, fluoride, hydroxide, sulfate, acetate, formate, and chloride. This is the reason why low recoveries were noticed for trifluralin which contains 3 Fluor atoms and because it is a non-polar compound (logP: 4.6). Low recovery was also observed for chlorfenvinphos because it contains a phosphate group and it has a strong interaction with Z-Sep sorbent [20]. The use of zirconium compared to the use of PSA, C₁₈, MgSO₄ and GCB combinations gave similar results regarding the analysis of carbamates by LC-MS/MS [20,22].

More recently, another new available sorbent, EMR-lipid has been used by Dias et al., and Parrilla-Vázquez et al. for more effective clean-up based on QuEChERS. EMR-lipid is a high selective lipid removal. This extraction procedure showed very good recovery results (70-120%), low RSDs (<20%) and LOQs results (10-50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) [18,19]. d-SPE EMR-lipid was also compared to Z-Sep, PSA-SPE and SPE procedure using zirconium. Better results in term of recoveries, RSD and matrix effect were demonstrated by d-SPE EMR [19]. With the use of EMR-lipid sorbent, matrix components are selectively removed without impacting the recoveries [19].

Another modification in the conventional QuEChERS extraction is the addition of the freezing-out step for further clean-up [18,19,21,28]. Fat co-extractives with limited solubility in acetonitrile precipitate and are removed, which reduce matrix effect. When low fat temperature precipitation or freezing is performed with dry ice, a faster fat precipitate is obtained (only 3-8 min) [18,19,31] compared to freezing in a standard freezer (between 2 and 24 h). The extraction method consisting of a freezing-out step followed by d-SPE EMR-lipid and analysis by GC-MS/MS gave the lowest RSD results (<4%) for a large number of compounds (213 pesticides) [19]. Other studies showed that in the case of olive oil extraction with modified QuEChERS and a freezing-out step, only for neonicotinoids no matrix

effect was observed. For most chemical groups (carbamates, organochlorines, organophosphorus, tri- azoles, and urea), the analytes presented a significant matrix effect [21].

4. Analytical detectors

4.1. GC-FID/ECD/NPD

GC has long been considered the method of choice for the determination of pesticide residues in olive oil and other vegetable oils, either with selective detectors such as the electron capture detector (ECD), flame ionization detector (FID) or nitrogen phosphorus detector (NPD) [58]. The results of the surveys showed that the determination of pesticide residues in vegetable oils showed good recovery rates. However, low LOQs could not be reached for all studied compounds. Good recoveries, between 85 and 115%, were achieved from the analysis of triazoles residues in rapeseed oil by GC-ECD [43] with RSD below 10%. The LOQs reached were between 3 and 300 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Other studies developed for the determination of 30 insecticides (organophosphorus, organochlorine, and pyrethroids) and 5 herbicides (triazines) in olive oil using SPE Envicarb cartridge followed by analysis on GC-ECD and NPD showed good recoveries between 70 and 106% [9] and LOQs between 2.6 and 47.8 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Other studies including 26 pesticides showed good recovery rates between 91 and 124% and reached LOQs between 2 and 20 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Good recovery rates were also obtained (80-106%) for the determination of 13 organophosphorus insecticides after a SPME procedure and GC-FID analysis [17]. However, the LOQs reached were between 16 and 30 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Therefore, despite the extraction and clean-up procedures, GC coupled to ECD, FID or NPD detectors were successfully used but for a small range of target pesticides depending on their elemental composition.

4.2. LC-DAD

A surprising recent reliance on LC-DAD approach for pesticide residues analysis in vegetable oils has been reported [10,11,25]. It is well known that the application using DAD is less expensive but low concentrations levels are more challenging to reach. The investigation criteria based on UV spectrum is not selective enough for a qualified determination. The lowest concentrations reached by LC-DAD for

chlorfenvinphos, terbuthylazine, lufenuron, flufenoxuron, and dimetomorph are in the range of 110-190 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, when a d-SPE based on zirconium sorbent was used. Lower LOQs (10-50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) can be reached by LC-MS/MS using the same extraction method [18]. Dimethoate and terbuthylazine are also analyzed by LC-DAD after a dual layer molecularly imprinted polymers (DL-MISPE). Good recovery rates are obtained but the LOQs levels reached are 5200 and 6 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, respectively [11]. Another study including pyrethroids (tetramethrin, fenpropathrin, cypermethrin, decamethrin, fenvalerate, acrinathrin, permethrin and bifenthrin) has also been developed by SPE with polystyrene coated magnetic nanoparticles (PSt/MNPs) followed by LC-DAD analysis [10]. Good recovery rates were obtained between 83 and 113% and RSD below 12%. The LOQs obtained in this case for eight pyrethroid compounds were between 0.1 and 0.2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$.

4.3. Single mass spectrometry

With the increase of the number of pesticides commercially available and with the need to reach lower LOQs; there was a fast shift to mass spectrometry analysis. Both GC-MS and LC-MS were used for pesticides residues analysis. There are few studies based on the analysis of pesticide residues in olive oil by single mass quadrupole [42,56,57] during the 10 last years due to the quick move to triple quadrupole MS for more selective and sensitive results.

Analysis performed by GC-MS for the determination of 40 pesticides showed good recovery rates (85-115%) and good repeatability (RSD < 10%). LOQ values reached were between 3 and 150 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ [42].

4.4. Tandem mass spectrometry

Besides the improvement of selectivity and sensitivity, triple quadrupole MS allows faster analysis with simultaneous quantification and identification of detected analytes [58], and reduces the signal to noise ratios [67]. Due to the inherent chromatographic method coupled to MS/MS, many studies reported the survey of pesticide residues in vegetables oils by tandem mass spectrometry [19,21,33,35]. Good recovery rates are obtained compared to those obtained with ECD, FID, NPD, and DAD detectors. It is essential to mention that recovery rates are also related to the extraction procedures. However, moving to tandem mass spectrometry allowed reaching lower LOQs. Guardia-Rubio et al. studied and compared the results

obtained by different detection techniques (ECD, TSD “Thermionic Sensitive Detection” and MS/MS). Shifting to tandem mass spectrometry allows reaching lower LOQ levels ($\leq 10 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) [34,45] compared to the ECD ($2\text{-}20 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) and TSD detectors ($5\text{-}20 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) [34]. It is important to note that analyses by GC-MS/MS cover a larger number of pesticides, reaching up to 213 pesticides [19] or more. Good recovery rates (73-103%) and low RSDs ($<10\%$) were obtained for the analysis of 100 pesticides by LC-Qtrap-MS/MS. Low LODs ($<1 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) and LOQs ($0.03\text{-}10 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) were reached [23]. The matrix effect obtained was tolerable (10-20%) for most of the pesticides [23]. 50% of the compounds exhibited an enhancement of results and 50% showed signal suppression [23]. Additionally, the pesticides fluometuron, difenoxuron, diuron, malathion, spynosin D, and spynosin A showed a higher degree of signal suppression (in the range of 22-27%), while cyromazine exhibited a strong signal suppression effect (45%) [23]. With the continuous increase of the number of authorized pesticides used in olive groves, the new substances are more polar, in line with integrated pest-management guidelines for a more environmentally friendly formulated pesticides; it is the case of some herbicides widely used in olive groves (amitrole, diuron, diquat, paraquat). Highly polar pesticides are not amenable on GC; they have poor MS source ionization or stability in the injector, column or detector of GC-MS/MS, which result in poor chromatographic performance. GC is amenable for pesticides of chemical classes which do not require derivatization including organochlorines, pyrethroids, organophosphorus pesticides, triazines, and chloroacetanilides, in addition to some transformation products of organochlorines, triazines, and phenylureas. In fact, GC-MS has an advantage over LC-MS for the organochlorines, due to their low polarity [68]. Certain polar chemical classes such as phenoxy acid herbicides and carbamates can still be analyzed by GC-MS methods but they require derivatization to make them GC amenable. To deal with more polar chemical classes of pesticides and for the simultaneous analysis of their transformation products, the use of LC-MS/MS became inevitable. LC-MS/MS has become a standard approach for the determination of a wide range of pesticides in complex matrix. Several studies in the case of olive oil and other vegetable oils have been published [18,20-22,24,26,38,45,46]. Taking in consideration olive oil production, polar compounds are removed by the cleaning step with water, making the survey of pesticide residues in olive oil mainly based on non-polar compounds, thus on GC-MS/MS analysis.

Both GC-MS/MS with electron ionization (EI) and LC-MS/MS using electrospray

ionization (ESI) are required to cover the full range of pesticide chemical classes and their transformation products. In general, satisfactory results of recoveries and repeatability are accomplished with both chromatographic analyzers (Table 3). The combination of GC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS gives high confidence in detecting analytes in real oil samples.

For more accuracy, selectivity and sensitivity, matrix effects should be taken in consideration because it can cause suppression or enhancement of the signal, resulting in wrong detection estimations. Matrix components can provide variation in the detector response. The matrix effect obtained by comparing the slopes of matrix-matched calibration curves with the slopes of the calibration curve in solvent shows high significance for oil matrices due to the ion suppression or enhancement by LC or GC-MS/MS. The enhancement or suppression of signal depends on the ionization procedure [69]. Ion suppression is most likely to occur with ESI process resulting in loss of sensitivity by LC-MS/MS [45]. Studies showed suppression of results for all compounds analyzed in oil matrices by LC-MS/MS; atrazine, diuron, terbuthylazine, omethoate, dimethoate, simazine, carbaryl, diuron, phosmet, methidathion, malathion, carbendazim, monocrotophos, spinosyn, and fenitrothion [22,24,37]. Except for sunflower oil, an enhancement of signal on LC-MS/MS was noted with some pesticides as azinphos-methyl, indoxacarb, malathion, metalaxyl, methamidophos, methidathion, thiacloprid, triadimefon, triadimenol, triazofos, and trifloxystrobin (~40%) [22]. For some other compounds analyzed by LC-MS/MS, matrix effect can be very high; 78% for spinosyn A, 89% for spinosyns D and K and 201% for spinosyn B. In the case of GC, a signal suppression or enhancement can occur depending on the compounds [22,37]. It is known that the matrix effects observed by GC-MS/MS in high fat-content commodities are stronger than when LC is applied [67]. GC-MS/MS has a few drawbacks over the LC-MS/MS method concerning the matrix effect. Matrix effect obtained by d-SPE EMR-lipid, combined with a freezing-out step was demonstrated to be $\pm 20\%$ by LC-MS/MS for a large scope of pesticides [18] and between $\pm 20\%$ and $\pm 50\%$ by GC-MS/MS [19].

One of the means to compensate matrix effects is the use of isotope-labeled internal standards. However, this is not practical in MRM due to the large scope of compounds analyzed. Another way is to perform the quantification with standard addition. Matrix effects can also be avoided by constructing matrix-matched standards for more accurate determination and for correct quantification of real oil samples. This latter approach is accepted by the European legislative framework [70]. Fortunately, the studies showed similar matrix effect for different kind of oils

(sunflower oil, olive oil, palm oil, and rapeseed oil) [22]. Therefore, the quantification of natural samples during routine analysis could be processed easily because of the reliance on one matrix-matched calibration curve for different kind of oils. This result was also confirmed by Dias et al., when an investigation of different kind of olive oils was studied by LC-MS/MS after the application of d-SPE EMR-Lipid [18]. Another study, by GC-MS/MS, showed that soybean oil has a slightly different matrix effect than sunflower and olive oil [19].

4.5. High resolution mass spectrometry

In a previous review published for the analysis of pesticides residues in olives and olive oils [67], no high resolution MS were available at that moment. High expectations were hoped with time-of-flight (ToF) coupled to MS detector for the development of multiresidue methods in olive oil. Recently, ToF-MS detectors became more popular. The advantage of ToF-MS is related to the high resolution full scan spectra that can reach 20,000 or more full-width at half maximum (FWHM) resolving power [8], the fast scanning of full spectrum and the accurate mass measurement. Evidently, ToF-MS is more selective and therefore lower LOQs results are achieved comparing to GC-NPD when the same extraction method was applied (MSPD) [14,40].

Studies have been published for the analysis of pesticide residues by LC-ToF-MS following L/L extraction. Seven polar pesticides: amitrole, cyromazine, diquat, paraquat, mepiquat, trimethyl sulfonium, and fosetyl aluminum were analyzed by LC-ToF-MS [37]. LOQs results were compared with the results obtained by LC-MS/MS.

Lower LOQs were reached by LC-ToF-MS ($0.1-10 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). LOQs reached by LC-MS/MS were between 0.5 and $57 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. However, some studies show different results. LOQs obtained by liquid partitioning treatment followed by LC-MS/MS for polar compounds as well (mepiquat, trimesium, amitrole, cyromazine and fosetyl-Al) were lower than with LC-ToF-MS [37]. Dimethoate, simazine, carbaryl, atrazine, diuron, terbuthylazine, and malathion were also analyzed by LC-ToF-MS in olive oil [13]. Good recovery rates were obtained between 73 and 104% with RSD between 5 and 13%. Low LOQs were obtained between 1.5 and $5 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Another study including simazine, atrazine, diuron and terbuthylazine showed good recovery rates (81-111%) and very low RSD (<4%) by LC-ToF-MS [14]. LC-ToF-MS has gained considerable interest for resolving matrix effect problems and for identification of

pesticides with exact mass measurements, with mass errors below 8 ppm [14,37]. However, the ion suppression observed by LC-ToF-MS is comparable to LC-MS/MS. Most of the compounds showed a decrease in the signal (simazine, carbaryl, atrazine, and terbuthylazine), except for diuron which showed a signal enhancement [13]. A study by high resolution ToF-MS showed a low matrix effect in the case of olive oil of approximately 20% suppression [37]. Other study showed suppression and enhancement of signal depending on the compounds (−14% to +36%) [14].

The scope of pesticides studied by LC-ToF-MS for pesticide residues in olive oil is not that large. A maximum of 7 compounds were analyzed in a row. By LC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS multiresidue analysis are more commonly reported. There were no studies benefitting from the fast scanning of high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) and based on untargeted analysis for oil samples. As for the analysis of pesticide residues in vegetable oils by GC-ToF-MS, no studies have been reported.

Orbitrap analyzers have been introduced for pesticides residues analysis in different commodities [71]. HRMS can be applied for quantitative purposes, but at the moment, they are focused on non-target screening analysis in food [72]. One study dealing with the analysis of pesticide residues in olive oil by the application of the full scan high resolution approach using LC-QExactive Orbitrap MS/MS has been published recently, covering 60 pesticides [73].

4.6. Biosensors followed by UV detection

Many enzymes based on electrochemical sensors have been described for the detection of selective pesticide residues (carbamates and organophosphates). Organic phase enzyme electrode (OPEE) has gained interest in the determination of compounds of low polarity in fatty matrices. Biosensors are too selective and cannot be used in multiresidue methods. Amperometric biosensors based on acetylcholinesterase have been widely studied. The concept is based on the ability of the pesticide to inhibit acetylcholinesterase reaction [74]. Enzymes are insoluble in organic solvents, they are immobilized by simple adsorption onto a solid or gel support [75]. A wide range of enzyme immobilization strategies have been studied for the analysis of pesticide residues in water. In the case of fatty matrices as oil, sensitive biosensors based on genetically engineered acetylcholinesterase immobilized on sol-gel matrix [76], in poly (vinyl alcohol)/Fe-Ni [77] or into electrospun chitosan/poly (vinyl alcohol) [78] have been reported. Studies were

focused on the oxidized product omethoate (dimethoate), malaoxon (malathion), N-bromosuccinimide (methidathion), pirimiphos methyl oxon (pirimiphos methyl), and phosmet oxon (phosmet). Good analytical performance was obtained in terms of recoveries (96-102%), reproducibility (1.6-3%) and storage stability. LODs obtained varied from 5000 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for omethoate, to 0.1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for methidathion, 1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for malaoxon, 0.2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for pirimiphos methyl oxon, and 0.1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for phosmet oxon.

Organic phase immuno electrodes (OPIE) are more selective than the OPEE [79]. However, for working in optimal conditions, many aspects have to be considered. The solvent choice is very important as it depends on many factors (hydrophobicity, logP and dielectric constant) as well as the choice of the electrochemical transducers and the immunosensors construction. Martini et al., has recently developed an OPIE for the analysis of triazinic (atrazine, simazine and terbuthylazine), organophosphate (parathion) and chlorurate (2,4-D and 2,4,5-T) in olive oil and industrial oil mill waste effluents [80,81]. Peroxidase enzyme was used and a Clark electrode was utilized as transducer. The solvent used was 50/50 chloroform-hexane. LOD reached was 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. This method was also applied for the analysis of triazinic, organophosphates and chlorurates in sunflower oil [81].

5. Real samples analysis

According to EFSA 2009 annual report [82], the percentage of compliance with EU MRLs for oil seeds was 95.7%. Among 161 samples, 80.1% had no pesticide residues detections. One pesticide residue was detected in 17.4%. The percentage of samples with more than 1 pesticide residue (2 pesticide residues) was 2.5%. According to the EFSA annual report in 2013 [83], imidacloprid residue was detected in one oil seed sample originated from United States at a level of 0.087 mg kg^{-1} exceeding the MRL (0.05 mg kg^{-1}). Acetamiprid was also detected in one oil seed sample originated from the United States at a concentration level of 0.32 mg kg^{-1} , not exceeding the MRL (0.7 mg kg^{-1}). According to EFSA annual report 2014, two pesticides were detected in oil seed samples exceeding the MRLs, fipronil at a concentration level of 0.014 mg kg^{-1} (MRL: 0.005 mg kg^{-1}) and fluopicolide at a level of 0.015 mg kg^{-1} (MRL: 0.01 mg kg^{-1}) [84].

Since olive oil was not included in previous EU-coordinated monitoring programs, no comparison of the 2012 results with previous years is possible. According to EFSA 2012 annual report [85], the percentage of compliance is 78%

among 794 samples of olive oil. 175 samples contained one or several pesticides. 39 samples (4.9%) contained multiple residues; up to five different pesticides. The most frequently found pesticides were chlorpyrifos (detected in 14.1% of the tested samples) and terbuthylazine (12.0%). There are other pesticides detected in olive oil in 2012 such as buprofezin, carbaryl, carbendazim, chlorpyrifos-methyl, chlorpyrifos, cyfluthrin, cypermethrin, deltamethrin, dimethoate, endosulfan, famoxadone, fenoxycarb, fenthion, frometanate, lambda-cyhalothrin, methidathion, methomyl, pendimethalin, phosmet, procymidone, propiconazole, propyzamide, pyraclostrobin, tebuconazole, terbuthylazine, and thiabendazole. Concerning terbuthylazine, residues above the MRL were detected in four samples. Similarly, endosulfan was detected in one sample, famoxadone in one sample and fenthion in three samples. The other detected pesticides did not exceed the MRLs.

From method validated studies and their application on real olive oil samples, some conclusions could be made regarding the most detected pesticides in real samples. 68% of compounds detected in olive oil are insecticides, 14% are fungicides, and 11% are herbicides. The most common detections (42%) include organophosphorus such as chlorpyrifos, fenthion, and ethion. 21% of the compounds detected correspond to the organochlorine class (alpha-endosulfan, beta-endosulfan, endosulfan sulfate, and endrin) and 17% are pyrethroids (cypermethrin, bifenthrin, deltamethrin, and fenvalerate). Azole (tetraconazole and tebuconazole) and triazine (simazine, atrazine and terbuthylazine) are also detected in olive oil samples. All detected pesticide residues are below the MRLs fixed by the EU authority.

6. Conclusions

It is well known that the determination of pesticide residues in oil matrices is a challenging analytical task because of the high triglyceride content of the samples. GC and LC coupled to MS/MS detector are generally the most suitable platform for multiresidue analysis. However, despite the selectivity and sensitivity provided, the extraction method often remains the main limiting step in the analysis of pesticide residues. A non-satisfactory removal of lipids from high lipid content products can affect recoveries causing signal enhancement. An excessive or non-selective removal of lipids may be accompanied with the removal of apolar pesticides, and may adversely affect target analytes recoveries causing signal suppression. The modifications implemented to the conventional QuEChERS

method including a freezing-out step before clean-up and the use of an EMR-lipid selective sorbent allow in general a high removal of co-extractives without great effect on pesticide recoveries. More research should be performed concerning the development of new selective sorbents in the future. There is a trend to increase the scope of pesticides residues analyzed in olive oil; multiresidue methods for the analysis of more than 200 pesticides have been recently reported. The LOQs of the proposed methods reported in different studies are below the MRLs, allowing the fulfillment of EU requirements. However, the use of high sensitive instrumentation allows not only reaching low LOQs but also decreasing the amount of sample injected, therefore a decrease of matrix effects. The emergence of high resolution mass spectrometry allows pesticide residues determination with accurate mass measurement and high resolving power, promising more selective and accurate results. HRMS can also allow the identification of non-target compounds, including not only pesticides but also environmental compounds. These two aspects of more sensitive instrumentation and accurate mass measurement will represent a step forward in oil analysis facilitating analytical achievements such as detecting frauds in olive oil and monitoring organic products.

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Table 1. MRLs (mg kg^{-1}) of common pesticides set by different world regulations [48,51].

Pesticides	EU	Codex Alimentarius		Japan Food Chemical Research Foundation	
	MRLs of olives for oil production multiplied by a PF of 5	Refined olive oil	Virgin olive oil	Edible olive oil (limited to virgin olive oil)	Edible olive oil (except virgin oil)
Carbaryl	0.1		25	25	
Fenthion	0.05		1	1	
Methidathion	0.1			2	
Dimethoate	0.6 ^a				0.05
Cypermethrin	0.25	0.5	0.5		
Trifloxystrobin	1.5	1.2	0.9		

^a Dimethoate is a non-fat soluble pesticide; the MRL of olives is multiplied by a factor of 0.3.

Table 2. MRLs of authorized pesticides for application on olive trees in Spain [51,52].

Classification	Pesticides authorized in Spain for application on olive trees	MRL mg kg ⁻¹ for olives for oil production	MRL mg kg ⁻¹ for olive oil by multiplying by a factor of 5
Herbicides	Amitrol	0.05	0.25
	Carfentrazone-ethyl	0.01	0.05
	Diflufenican	0.2	1
	Dicloprop	0.05	0.25
	Diflufenican	0.2	1
	Diquat	0.05	0.25
	Diuron	0.02	0.1
	Ethephon	10	50
	Fazasulfuron	0.01	0.05
	Fluroxypyr	0.01	0.05
	Flumioxazine	0.05	0.25
	Glyphosate	1	5
	Oxyflurofen	1	5
	Fluometuron	0.01	0.05
	Insecticides	Fenoxycarb	1
Ethofenprox		0.01	0.05
Buprofezin		5	25
Chlorpyrifos		0.05	0.25
Deltamethrin		1	1.5 ^a
Fungicides	Folpet	0.02	0.1
	Fosetyl-Al	2	10
	Difencconazole	2	10
	Dodine	20	100
Insecticides/ acaricides	Cypermethrin	0.05	0.38 ^a
	Dimethoate	2	0.6 ^a
	Phosmet	3	15

^a PF of dimethoate: 0.3, PF of cypermethrin: 7.5, PF of deltamethrin: 1.5.

Table 3. Summary of extraction and analytical procedures used for the determination of pesticide residues in olive oil and other vegetable oils over a 12th year period (2006-2017), including recoveries, RSDs, LODs, and LOQs.

	Analytes	Oil type/amount of matrix	Extraction method	Analytical instrument	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)	LOD ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Year	Ref
GPC	Organochlorines (a-endosulfan, b-endosulfan, endosulfan sulfate)	Olive oil	Oven transfer adsorption desorption	GPC-GC		≤ 14	7-67	15-134	2006	[32]
	100 pesticides	Olive oil (4 g)	Dissolution with 20 mL of n-hexane and extraction with acetonitrile followed by GPC	GC-MS/MS	70-110		≤ 1.9	≤ 3.6	2007	[33]
	26 pesticides	Virgin and refined olive oil (2 g)	Dissolution with 2 mL of n-hexane and extraction with 10 mL acetonitrile + 3 mg sodium sulfate followed by GPC	GC-MS/MS	83.8-110.3	5-8	0.1-1.6	0.3-3.6	2006	[34]
	32 organochlorine, organophosphorus and organonitrogen pesticides	Virgin olive oil (2 g)	Dissolution with 10 mL of n-hexane saturated with acetonitrile, extraction 3 times with 10 mL acetonitrile saturated with n-hexane, followed by GPC	GC-TSD GC-ECD GC-MS/MS	82-100 91-124 89-105	9-20 1-8 4-14	2-10 0.5-10 0.2-10	5-20 2-20 0.5-10	2006	[35]
d-SPE	26 pesticides	Olive oil and olive pomace oil	2 mL n-hexane and 10 mL acetonitrile + 3 mg sodium sulfate followed by GPC	GC-MS/MS	84-110	3-7.8		10	2006	[36]
	165 pesticides	Edible oil: olive, soya, sunflower (15 g)	Extraction with 15 mL acetonitrile, partitioning step: 6 g MgSO_4 , 1.5 g NaCl, 1.5 g sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate and 0.75 g disodium hydrogen citrate sesquihydrate. Clean-up step: freezing-out followed by d-SPE EMR-lipid	LC-MS/MS	70-120	< 20		10-50	2016	[18]
	213 pesticides	Soybean, sunflower and olive oil (15 g)	Extraction with 15 mL acetonitrile, partitioning step: 6 g MgSO_4 , 1.5 g NaCl, 1.5 g sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate and 0.75 g disodium hydrogen citrate sesquihydrate. Clean-up step: freezing-out followed by d-SPE EMR-lipid	GC-MS/MS	70-120	< 4		10-20	2016	[19]
	30 carbamates	Vegetable oil (3 g)	7 mL of water + 10 mL acetonitrile, QuEChERS (4 MgSO_4 + 1 g NaCl) d-SPE with zirconium clean-up sorbent (150 mg Z-Sep ⁺ and 150 mg MgSO_4)	LC-MS/MS	74-101	< 10		0.09-2	2014	[20]
	32 different chemical groups of pesticides	Olive oil (5 g)	10 mL Acetonitrile + freezer (-20°C) for 12 hours + clean-up of 6 mL extract (150 mg PSA, 12.5 mg GCB, 900 mg MgSO_4)	GC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS	70-120	20-25	3		2013	[21]
	44 pesticides	Olive oil (3 g)	7 mL water + 10 mL acetonitrile, d-SPE (250 mg PSA, 250 mg C_{18} , 250 mg GCB and 750 mg MgSO_4) d-SPE using combination of PSA- C_{18} (excluding GCB)	LC-MS/MS	52-131 53-109	8-41 3-19	1-5 10-50		2012	[22]
	100 pesticides	Olive oil (3 g)	d-SPE using PSA (excluding GCB and C_{18}) 7 mL water + 10 mL acetonitrile, d-SPE (750 mg MgSO_4 , 250 mg PSA, 250 mg C_{18} , 250 mg GCB)	LC-MS-Qtrap	76-110 73-130	3-18 < 10	10-50 ≤ 1	0.03-10	2007	[23]
	16 pesticides	Olive oil (10 g)	10 mL acetonitrile, d-SPE (750 mg MgSO_4 , 50 mg	LC-MS/MS,	70-109	< 20		10-50	2007	[24]

			PSA, 50 mg C ₁₈ , 50 mg GCB)	DSI-GC-MS (SIM Mode)								
	21 pesticides	Edible oil (6 g)	14 mL water + 20 mL acetonitrile, Partitioning step: 8 g MgSO ₄ , 2g NaCl. Clean-up: 500 mg Z-Sep	LC-DAD	50-130	<15		50-790	2016	[25]		
	28 multi-class pesticides	Soybean oil (5 g)	10 mL acetonitrile, Low temperature fat precipitation followed by d-SPE	GC-MS	70-110	<20		20-250	2007	[26]		
	9 organophosphorus	Peanut oil (5 g)	10 mL acetonitrile, Freezing overnight at -20°C, 0.5 g of Na ₂ SO ₄ , addition of 100 mg of Carbon nanotubes and 1g of neutral alumina, final dissolution with hexane		85.9-114.3	<8.46	0.7-1.6		2011	[27]		
	105 pesticides	Olive oil (3 g)	7 mL water + 10 mL acetonitrile, d-SPE: 250 mg PSA, 250 mg C ₁₈ , 250 mg GCB, 750 mg MgSO ₄	LC-MS/MS	70-130 for 72% of analytes			10	2010	[29]		
	95 pesticides	Soybean oil (5 g)	Dissolution with 5 mL n-hexane, extraction twice with 5 mL acetonitrile, Addition of 0.5 g MgSO ₄ , freezing at -20°C for 4 hours. Clean-up with 50 mg Florisil and 100 mg MgSO ₄	GC-MS/MS	82-107	2-15		40-160	2010	[28]		
	Multiresidue class	Oil crops (5 g)	5 mL water + 20 mL acetonitrile, Reversed d-SPE using amine modified graphene (500 mL of CH ₃ NH-G aqueous solution)	GC-MS/MS	70.5-100	13	0.1-8.3		2013	[30]		
	32 multicalss pesticides	Edible oil (5 g)	10 mL acetonitrile, d-SPE using 40 mg AC, 150 mg PSA and 300 mg MgSO ₄	GC-MS/MS	62-110				2014	[31]		
	60 pesticides	Olive oil	QuEChERS	LC-QExactive- Orbitrap MS/MS				0.1-122.7	2017	[73]		
L/L extraction	7 polar pesticides: amitrole, cyromazine, diquat, paraquat, mepiquat, trimethylsulfonium, fosetylaluminium Imdacloprid, thiacloprid, spinosyn	Olive oil (10 g)	10 mL water + 10 mL acetonitrile with 1 % HCOOH	LC-MS/MS and LC- ToF-MS	58-120 MS/ MS			0.5-57 (MSMS) and 0.1-10 (ToF-MS)	2016	[37]		
		Olive oil (1 g)	5 mL acetonitrile, partitioning with 2 g MgSO ₄ and 3 g NaCl.	LC-DAD and LC-ESI/ MS	80-119	1-19	1-8	10	2011	[40]		
	Fenthion and its metabolites	Olive oil (10 g)	10 mL n-hexane	GC-NPD	63-115	6-14	6-40	100	2007	[12]		
	Diquat and paraquat	Virgin olive oil (2 g)	2 mL n-hexane + 2 mL of 10 mM aqueous solution of HFBA, L/L extraction followed by freezing for 2 hours at 4°C	LC-ESI-MS/MS	92-112	<7	4		2006	[38]		
	Triazolespesticides (penconazole, hexaconazole, diniconazole, tebuconazole, triticonazole)	All edible oils (sunflower oil, olive oil, grape seed oil, and corn oil) (1 mL)	5 mL hexane, microextraction procedure with dimethyl sulfoxide	GC-FID	71-96	<5	2.2-6.1	7.3-20	2015	[41]		
	40 pesticides	Vegetable oils	Dissociated extraction	GC-MS	85-115	<10	1-10	3-150	2016	[42]		
	19 azole class fungicides	Rapeseed oil (5 g)	15 mL hexane saturated with acetonitrile, dissociated extraction	GC-ECD	85-115	<10		3-300	2014	[43]		

MSPD	Spinosad 14 organophosphorus	Olive oil (2 g) Soybean oil, sesame oil, peanut oil	10 mL acetonitrile Extraction with acetonitrile, low-temperature clean-up PSA, C ₁₈ , MgSO ₄	LC/ESI-MS/MS GC-FPD, GC-MS	87-116 >50	1-8 <15			2011 2007	[46] [26]
	Fenthion and its metabolites	Olive oil (0.2 g)	Oil blended with NH ₂ , MSPD using a column of 1g of Florisil, dryness with MgSO ₄ , Elution with 3 × 5 mL acetonitrile	GC-NPD	67-98	5-11	2-10	30	2007	[12]
	Dimethoate, simazine, carbaryl, atrazine, diuron, terbuthylazine, malathion	Olive oil (5 g)	Dissolution with 5 mL n-hexane, MSPD (Florisil-GCB), elution with 15 mL acetonitrile	LC-Q-ToF-MS	73.7-104.2	5.3-13.4	1.5-5	3.6-9	2011	[13]
	Simazine, atrazine, diuron and terbuthylazine	Olive oil (5 g)	15 mL petroleum ether saturated with acetonitrile, MSPD (homogenization with 2 g aminopropyl-bonded silica and transfer to a 2 g column of Florisil, elution with 2 × 5 mL acetonitrile)	LC-ESI-ToF-MS	81-111	2-4	1-5	5	2006	[14]
SPME	14 organochlorines	Edible vegetable oils (0.5 g)	3.5 g of 40% (w:w) sulfuric acid-impregnated silica gel, introduction to a SPE reservoir with a polypropylene frit and 0.8 g silica gel as co-column, elution with n-hexane/ dichloromethane (70:30, v/v)	GC-ECD	96.9-105.3	<15	0.04-0.74		2014	[16]
	9 organophosphorus insecticides and 4 metabolites (omethoate, malaoxon, fenthion, sulfoxide, fenthion, sulfone)	Olive oil (5 g)	Headspace SPME (with PDMS fibers)	GC-FID	80-106%	<10	6-10	16-30	2006	[17]
	35 pesticides	Olive oil (5 g)	Dissolution in 5 mL n-hexane and extraction with 10 mL acetonitrile, SPE Envicarb cartridge and final clean-up with a normal-phase Diol SPE cartridge	GC-ECD, GC-NPD	70-106	2.4-17.4	0.6-14.5 (NPD) 0.8-13.1 (ECD)	1.6-47.8 (NPD) 2.6-43.3 (ECD)	2006	[9]
	Pyrethroids: tetramethrin, fenpropathrin, cypermethrin, decamethrin, fenvalerate, acrinathrin, Dimethoate and terbuthylazine	Vegetable oils: soybean oil, canola oil, sunflower oil, corn oil and virgin olive oil (5 g)	20 mL acetonitrile, Freezer at -20°C for at least 24 hours, dilute with 80 mL water, SPE, transfer to a flask with 70 mg of Polystyrene coated magnetic nanoparticles	LC-DAD	83-113	<12	0.0290 -0.0475	0.0891 -0.1994	2017	[10]
SPE	Chlortoluron, diuron, atrazine, simazine, terbuthylazin-desethyl	Olive oil (1g)	Dilution with 10 mL n-heptane, DL-MISPE cartridge, elution with 2 mL n-heptane/CH ₂ Cl ₂ and later with 2 mL methanol	LC-DAD	94-95	0.1-0.3	DIM: 1600 TER.: 2	DIM:5200 TER:6	2016	[11]
	9 organophosphorus	Virgin olive oil (3 mL)	Dissolution with hexane, Carbon nanotubes, cleaning with 3 mL hexane and elution with 0.5 mL ethyl acetate	GC-MS		<9	1.5-3		2009	[62]
	9 organophosphorus	Olive oil (5 g)	Dissolution acetonitrile/dichloromethane 90:10, v/v, Microwave assisted extraction + Envicarb cartridge,	GC-FPD and GC -MS	>73 except for fenthion and	≤11			2008	[59]

OPEE/OPI E	3 organophosphorus pesticides (malathion, dimethoate and methidathion)	Olive oil	elution with 3 mL dichloromethane L/L extraction. Solegel immobilization of acetylcholinesterase	Diode array spectrophotometer	chlorpyrifos ~100		0.1-5000	2013	[76]
	Pyrimiphos-methyl	Olive oil	L/L extraction, AChE immobilized into electrospun chitosan/poly (vinyl alcohol)	UV spectrophotometer	96-102	1.6-2	0.2	2016	[77]
	Phosmet	Olive oil	L/L extraction, AChE immobilized in poly (vinyl alcohol)/Fe-Ni	UV spectrophotometer		3	0.1	2016	[78]
	Atrazine, simazine, terbuthylazine, parathion, 2,4-D and 2,4,5-T	Olive oil and industrial oil mill waste	L/L extraction, immunosensors	UV spectrophotometer			10	2015	[80]
	Atrazine, simazine, terbuthylazine, parathion, 2,4-D and 2,4,5-T	Sunflower oil	L/L extraction, immunosensors	UV spectrophotometer			10	2015	[81]
